

THE ALKALOIDS OF *RAUWOLFIA CANESCENS*, LINN. PART II

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Rauwolscine is hydrolysed by aqueous alkali to rauwolscinic acid, $C_{20}H_{24}O_3N_2$, which contains one CO_2H group. It can be reconverted into rauwolscine by esterification with methyl alcohol. Ethyl, *n*-propyl and *n*-butyl esters of rauwolscinic acid have also been described, as also some of their salts. The colour reactions of rauwolscinic acid are similar to those of the parent compound and yohimbine. The ultraviolet absorption spectra of rauwolscine and yohimbine have been found to be very similar.

In a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 33) the preliminary examination of a new alkaloid, rauwolscine ($C_{21}H_{26}O_3N_2$), isolated from *Rauwolfia Canescens*, has been reported. It was found to give colour reactions similar to those of yohimbine and was found to undergo hydrolysis by means of concentrated aqueous ammonia at room temperature to an acid, rauwolscinic acid. The same acid has now been obtained by hydrolysis of the alkaloid with aqueous potassium hydroxide in quantitative yield.

The acid forms pale yellow prisms, m. p, $262-64^\circ$ (decomp.), having $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +136.8^\circ$. It yielded a crystalline hydrochloride and a picrate. It can be esterified with methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl and *n*-butyl alcohol. These esters are well defined crystalline compounds and form crystalline hydrochlorides. The analytical data of these esters and their salts support the formula, $C_{20}H_{24}O_3N_2$, previously suggested for rauwolscinic acid. The observed equivalent weight of this monobasic acid is also in good agreement with the above molecular formula.

The colour reactions of rauwolscinic acid are very similar to those of rauwolscine or yohimbine, as will be evident from the following table.

Reagent.	Colour reactions of rauwolscinic acid.
Conc. H_2SO_4	Blue with a violet tinge, gradually fades away to pale green.
Conc. $H_2SO_4 + K_2Cr_2O_7$	Deep blue, then violet, finally purplish brown.
Erdmann's reagent	Purplish brown, then green and finally yellow.
Froehde's reagent	Indigo blue, gradually fades away to olive green, then greyish and finally dirty yellow.
Mandelin's reagent	Olive green, quickly changing to brown, then reddish brown and finally purplish brown.

From the general chemical behaviour it was suggested in Part I that the main features of the structures of rauwolscine and yohimbine might prove to be very similar. Confirmation of this supposition is now available

from a comparison of the ultraviolet absorption spectra of the hydrochlorides of the two bases which are graphically represented in Fig. 1. Yohimbine hydrochloride (Merck) showed a well defined absorption band with the maxima at $2740\text{\AA}$ and a minima at $2430\text{\AA}$. The corresponding figures for rauwolfscine hydrochloride are $2750\text{\AA}$ and $2450\text{\AA}$ respectively.

FIG. 1

Absorption curves 1 and 2 refer respectively to hydrochlorides of yohimbine in water (dilution 1 in 20,000) and of Rauwolfscine in water (dilution 1 in 27,000)

According to Karschulin (*Arch. Hemijū*, 1931, 5, 227) the absorption spectra of yohimbine and yohimbic acid are similar to those of indole but not to those of quinoline. One might consequently infer that rauwolfscine contains an indole nucleus. This inference has already received independent support by the degradation of rauwolfscine to an indole derivative which will be described in a subsequent communication.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

rauwolescnic Acid.—When rauwolescine (0.5 g.) was heated on the water-bath with 10% aqueous potassium hydroxide (20 c.c.) for 4-5 hours, the base went into complete solution. The brownish yellow solution was filtered and the clear filtrate concentrated on the water-bath to about 15 c.c. Acidification with *N*/2 acetic acid (avoiding excess) precipitated rauwolescnic acid, yield 86%. The product was twice crystallised from boiling water when pale yellow prisms, m. p. 262-64° (decomp.) were obtained. The acid (0.254 g.) lost 0.0138 g. in weight when dried at 125-30° for 4 hours in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 . [Found: H_2O , 5.43. $C_{20}H_{24}O_3N_2$, H_2O requires H_2O , 5.03 per cent. Found in dry specimen: C, 70.11; H, 7.22; Equiv.*, 349, 350. $C_{20}H_{24}O_3N_2$ requires C, 70.58; H, 7.06 per cent. Equiv. (monobasic), 340].

The substance is sparingly soluble in water and insoluble in alcohol, benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate, ether and petroleum ether. 0.0590 G. of substance in 50 c.c. of water showed a rotation of +0.13° in 0.5 dcm. tube at 23°, whence $[\alpha]_D^{23} = +136.8^\circ$.

The Hydrochloride of Rauwolescnic Acid.—The acid (0.15 g.) was dissolved in hot 2*N*-hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.). The star-shaped colourless crystals, which separated out on boiling, were recrystallised from hot water, m. p. 255.5°-257.5° (decomp.). (Found: Loss on drying at 120°-25° for 3½ hrs. in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 , 11.2. $C_{20}H_{24}O_3N_2$, HCl, $\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires H_2O , 10.7 per cent. Found in anhydrous specimen: Cl, 9.42. $C_{20}H_{24}O_3N_2$, HCl requires Cl, 9.43 per cent).

The Picrate.—An orange precipitate was obtained on treating an aqueous solution of the acid with aqueous picric acid. Crystallised from alcohol it formed shining brick-red plates, m. p. 232-34° (decomp.). [Found in specimen dried† at 115-120° for 4 hours in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : N, 11.40. $C_{20}H_{24}O_3N_2$. $C_6H_2OH(NO_2)_3$, C_2H_5OH requires N, 11.38 per cent].

The Ethyl Ester.—A stream of dry hydrogen chloride was passed through a suspension of rauwolescnic acid (0.25 g.) in absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) at 0°, till saturated. The acid gradually passed into solution and the clear solution on standing overnight deposited colourless shining needles of the ester hydrochloride, yield 0.26 g. The crystals were collected, washed with cold absolute alcohol and recrystallised from hot water, m. p. 262-64° (decomp.). The substance did not suffer any loss on drying in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 3 hours at 120°. (Found: Cl, 8.84. $C_{22}H_{28}O_3N_2$, HCl requires Cl, 8.77 per cent).

* Excess of standard alkali was added to a known weight of the acid and titrated back rapidly with standard acid using phenolphthalein as indicator.

† No loss in weight was observed on drying.

The hydrochloride (0.07 g.) was dissolved in warm water (25 c.c.) and the solution was rapidly cooled and made just alkaline with ammonia. The shining, colourless needles, which were thus obtained, were washed with cold water and twice crystallised from ethyl alcohol when the ester melted at 234-36° (decomp.). Further crystallisations did not raise the m. p. The ester suffered no loss in weight when dried at 110°-15° for 4 hours in *vacuo* over P₂O₅. (Found: C, 72.03; H, 7.47. C₂₂H₂₆O₃N₂ requires C, 71.74; H, 7.6 per cent).

The Picrate of the Ethyl Ester.—An orange precipitate was obtained on mixing ethereal solutions of the ester and picric acid. Crystallised from alcohol, it formed shining orange-yellow plates, m. p. 179.5°-181.5° (decomp.). [Found in specimen dried at 100°-105° for 3 hours in *vacuo* over P₂O₅: N, 11.90. C₂₂H₂₆O₃N₂. C₆H₂(OH)(NO₂)₃ requires N, 11.72 per cent].

The n-Propyl Ester of Rauwolfscinic Acid.—It was prepared in the same way as ethyl ester. The hydrochloride was purified by crystallisation from hot water when it formed colourless, slender needles, m.p. 264-66° (decomp.). It suffered no loss in weight when dried at 110-15° for 4 hours in *vacuo* over P₂O₅. (Found: Cl, 8.56. C₂₂H₃₀O₃N₂, HCl requires Cl, 8.40 per cent).

The free base was liberated by the method followed in case of the ethyl ester, 0.16 g. of the hydrochloride requiring 50 c.c. water for complete solution. The shining silky rods of the *n*-propyl ester were crystallised from ethyl alcohol and had m. p. 206-8° (decomp.) (Found in specimen dried at 105-10° for 4 hours in *vacuo* over P₂O₅: C, 72.06; H, 8.04. C₂₂H₃₀O₃N₂ requires C, 72.25; H, 7.85 per cent).

The n-Butyl Ester Hydrochloride of Rauwolfscinic Acid, prepared as usual, melted at 251-53° (decomp.). (Found in specimen dried at 120° for 4 hours in *vacuo* over P₂O₅: Cl, 8.16. C₂₄H₃₂O₃N₂, HCl requires Cl, 8.2 per cent). The free base, *n-butyl ester of rauwolfscinic acid*, was prepared by the method described under the *n*-propyl ester. It formed pale, yellow shining needles (alcohol). It froths up at 105°-6° and melts at 181-182.5° (decomp.). (Found in specimen dried at 75-80° for 4 hours in *vacuo* over P₂O₅: C, 72.44; H, 8.2. C₂₄H₃₂O₃N₂ requires C, 72.72; H, 8.09 per cent).

The picrates of the propyl and butyl esters could not be prepared.

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